

BLENDING LEARNING AS AN INSTRUCTIONAL PEDAGOGY FOR SMART PLANNING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT:

Today, technological innovations, and the internet, have significantly affected educational processes, serving as a catalyst for change. Educational institutes and organizations have a wide selection of learning approaches and options today. In addition to all other learning environments, online learning has become the most powerful and effective tool of learning. Web 2.0 tools have made the Internet interactive and have helped overcome many problems of learning until now.

Now that the internet is an integral part of the educational system, it is also essential that English language teachers are aware of synchronous and asynchronous web resources available along with their traditional classroom teaching in order to facilitate substantial learning of the English language.

This paper is an attempt to use blended learning as an instructional pedagogy for the development of a smart lesson, allowing teachers to cater to the 21st century learning needs of learners, while also utilizing synchronous and asynchronous web resources for communication, presentations, lectures, and various other web-based resources for the study of English.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Instructional Pedagogy, ELT, Smart Plan*

1. INTRODUCTION

The term blended learning refers to learning that is facilitated by an effective combination of different modes of delivery, models of teaching, and styles of learning, and applying them in an interactively meaningful learning environment. e.g. a mix of live e-learning, face-to-face elements, self-paced learning, computer-mediated and mobile learning along with classroom learning used to achieve the objectives of learning. It could simply be the use of PowerPoint presentations, DVD, video, podcast, videoconferencing or use of various websites along with traditional classroom teaching.

Blended learning approach intends to extend the classroom making learning more learner centric, and provides a unique learning experience in space and time there is no fixed formula for the use of technologies in blended learning program due to the variation in the nature of course content, learning objectives, and learning profile. The key issue about blending is not to make technology exciting but fitting technology seamlessly into a program appropriate for learning in this digital age blended learning can provide the best solution for learning English language provided it is thoughtfully used by developing a smart plan along with the traditional classroom teaching which also facilitates the learning of technology skill .

2. Literature Review

Blended learning is a method that has proved to be not only effective in terms of learning outcomes, but ranks high on ratings of satisfaction with students and instructors (Dzuiban, Hartman & Moskal, 2004). Yet there has been little consideration of the blended approach.

When implemented effectively, blended learning program, can make better use of instructional resources and facilities, and increase class availability thus speeding up the pathway to graduation for students (Dzuiban et al, 2004).

Today the student's demand of technology is very different than it was 10 years ago,

In present time they grew up on the internet, although represents only a small portion of the total college population. The Net Generation expects technology integration and having something online is not enough (Kravik & Caruso, 2005).

In another study of pedagogical practices, it was found that only 23–45 percent of online instructors surveyed actually used online activities related to critical and creative thinking, hands-on performances, interactive labs, data analysis, and scientific simulations, although 40 percent of the participants said those activities were highly important in online learning environments (Bonk, 2004).

Over the past decade, countless efforts have sought to integrate emerging Internet technologies into the teaching and learning process in higher education. Studies have also reported cases related to the use of blogs to promote student collaboration and reflection (Baggaley 2003). Some researchers also have promoted the possibility of using wikis for online student collaboration (Lamba, 2004).

Podcasting has also started to garner attention from educators for its instructional use (Sloan, 2005).

3. Objective

- To develop a module for blended Learning.
- To develop a Smart Plan for the teaching of the English Language.
- To train teachers for techno-pedagogic skills.

4. Method of Development of Smart Lesson Plan

From the point of view of instructional design, the researcher used a hybrid approach in this paper. To develop a Smart Plan, a blended learning module was developed first that laid out a roadmap for developing a blended plan for ELT.

With the combination of traditional and online methods, a Smart Plan on Helen Keller was developed that could be used by English language teachers to make the learning of English more systematic, organized, and engaging with the help of web and e-resources. It would also help the teachers to develop the techno-pedagogical skills as

they develop their Smart Plans. An example of an English Smart Plan and the module will catalyze illuminating, and eliciting further ideas for more comprehensive Smart Plans tailored to meet the needs of a specific teacher.

1 Classroom learning	2 Online learning	3 Blend
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Face-to-face interaction with students • Using traditional lesson plans • The demonstration, illustration, discussion, question-answer, and lecture methods can all be used 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online interaction with the students - Use of technology integrated lesson plans - Learning through virtual classroom - Use of online resources Educational websites Interactive videos Audios - Other multimedia features - Interaction with global learners and teachers. - Facilitates online skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blend of the two (classroom and online learning) - Teacher along with the online resources facilitates learning - Use of various synchronous and asynchronous resources takes place along with the traditional teaching. e.g., Video and audio conferencing Webcasting, online interactions and other asynchronous resources are used to enhance learning.

Table 1: Blended Learning Modul

Based on the module a Smart Plan on “Helen Keller” was developed to teach English language.

<u>TEACHING POINT</u>	<u>TEACHER’S ACTIVITY</u>			<u>STUDENT’S ACTIVITY</u>	<u>SKILLS INVOLVED AND PRACTICED</u>
Introductory Questions	<p>Teacher will use the power point presentation on great personalities who were visually impaired and will ask following questions.</p> <p>http://www.authorstream.com/Presentation/romasmart-1653305-blindness/</p> <p>Q1. Which personality impressed you the most?</p> <p>Q2. Why did you admire that personality?</p> <p>Q3. Why being handicapped is not a limitation to be successful in life?</p> <p>Q4. Which factors are important to succeed in life?</p> <p>Q5. How a blind person can achieve success in life?</p> <p>Let us see what were the factors that contributed towards Helen Keller's Success</p>			Students will answer the questions	<p>Internet browsing</p> <p>Working on word processor</p> <p>making power point presentation and uploading it</p> <p>Hyper linking required sites</p> <p>Working online</p>
Presentation Model reading	<p>The pupil teacher will read aloud from Helen's free online book with proper pronunciation, pauses, articulation and expression</p> <p>https://www.storyjumper.com/book/read/10890142/Helen-Keller-</p>			Students will be directed to Helen Keller's online museum and given an overview of her life.	Use of educational websites
Pronunciation Drill This can be done by the teacher or by using Google Translate	<u>Word</u> Healthy	<u>Phonetic transcription</u> helθi	<u>Common usage</u> Hell–thee	Students will pronounce the word	use of asynchronous and synchronous

<p>https://translate.google.co.in/?hl=en&tab=wT or www.howjsay.com for appropriate pronunciation drill</p>	<p>Alabama Parents Disappointed</p>	<p>æləbæmə peərənts dɪsəpɔɪntəd</p>	<p>a-lay-b-ma pair-rents dis-a-point-ted</p>	<p>correctly. With the help of the website</p>	<p>resources</p>
<p>LOUD READING</p>	<p>The pupil teacher will ask the students to read the online passage one by one (mistakes will be corrected)</p> <p>http://books.google.co.in/books?id=LM3VxWdQaoYC&printsec=frontcover&dq=helen+keller&hl=en&sa=X&ei=-a0bUYaqLYiurAfzkICgAg&ved=0CDwQ6AEwAQ</p>		<p>Students will participate in reading and can check their pronunciations of difficult words on</p> <p>http://translate.google.co.in/?hl=en&tab=wT or http://www.howjsay.com/</p>	<p>online reading skills, using e-books and other applications</p>	

WORD EXPOSITION	Word	Meaning	Device /technique	Detailed explanation	
<p>Teacher will use various devices such as framing a sentence, animation, video or image to make clear the meaning of the word</p>	Dearly	Very much or very strongly	Sentence	Ramesh loves his parents dearly.	Use of online interactive dictionary
	Disappointed	Fail to fulfil the desire or expectation	Video <iframe width="420" height="315" src="//www.youtube.com/embed/e9mOvGR6XeA" frameborder="0" allowfullscreen></iframe>	video showing the face expression	http://www.snappwords.com/?lookup=dearl
	Illness	A state of being	http://www.slideshare.net/romasmart/	Picture showing illness He is a bright student since he always comes first in class	Use of embed code of youtube video Use of slide share, a web resource

	Bright	unwell Clever	picture-34942501 Sentence		
Written Work and Supervision	The pupil teacher will ask the students to copy the words meanings in their exercise books and she will supervise the class.		The students will copy the word meanings in their exercise books.		
Silent Reading	Pupil teacher will ask the students to read a book http://books.google.co.in/books?id=ILlGjSjBCP4C&printsec=frontcover&dq=helen+keller&hl=en&sa=X&ei=-a0bUYaqLYiurAfzkICgAg&ved=0CEMQ6AEwAg silently.		The students will read the passage silently.		using e-books, libraries etc.
Comprehension Questions	Students will Watch the video http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gv1uLfF35Uw and will answer following questions Q1. Where was Helen Keller born? Q2. What happened when Helen was a baby? Q3. Who was the teacher of helen keller? Q4. What is braille? Q5. Who was the inventor of braille?		Students will answer the questions. Students will answer with the help of video		
WORD STRUCTURE	Words would tell her everything she		Know. Have pizza for	The students will	

	The children Asha I	Wanted to	dinner. Do Ph. D after her masters' course. Buy new clothes for my birthday	participate and interact to frame a correct Word structure	
Recapitulation	<u>Recap will be done by playing a quiz</u> onlinehttp://www.surfnetkids.com/games/helen_keller_quiz.htm		Students will participate in the quiz		
HOME ASSIGNMENT	Teacher will post an assignment on google classroom and students will post their opinions about physically challenged ones on GC			Use of synchronous and asynchronous online resources, e.g., UltimateEdu, edmodo, wiziq etc.	

Table 2: Smart Plan on Helen Keller

5. Conclusion

- The Smart Plan based on blended learning as an instructional pedagogy for ELT can be very helpful for the 21st-century learner.
- Smart planning can be used both in the classroom and online to teach and learn the subject matter more comprehensively and help to stay connected with the student round the clock.
- The problem of missing the class is also overcome by the availability of the various web resources teaching the content on the internet.
- The teachers and learners can develop many techno skills
- Blending internet resources along with traditional classroom teaching facilitates learning and makes it interesting for learners to overcome geographical, financial, and time barriers.
- It is time now to develop blended strategies like this which gives learners more and more options to learn and grow along with this classroom teaching.

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Note: Summary of the lesson is available at

<http://www.thinglink.com/scene/357833280088702976?buttonSource=userPage>

This lesson plan can be viewed at <http://romasmartjoseph.blogspot.in/>